

THARO THONGBA

Manipuri River Snail Curry

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Photos by Thoithoi Khaidem

Tharoi Thongba is a Manipuri snail curry made with vegetable, herbs and spices flavoured with *Ngari* (Manipuri fermented fish). This dish can be had straight as an evening snack or consumed with rice.

The Manipuri people prepare it on the eve of *Cheiraoba* (Manipur Lunar calendar new year) which usually falls in the month of April.

Here is the recipe for *Lai Tharoi Thongba* which is more expensive compared with the other varieties of snails found in the state, like Tharoi Ningkhaibi (*Angulyagra oxytropis*) and Labuktharoi (*Cipangopaludina lecythoides*, and *Bellamya crassa*).

There are two common varieties of *Lai Tharoi* which are eaten in Manipur. They are *Brotia costula* and Common *Melania*. They are considered as healthy and nutritious.

Ingredients:

*500 gm fresh water river snail (cut the end of snail).

* Potato (cut into half)

* 2-3 Rhizomes of *Loklei* (Butterfly Ginger Lily) peeled.

* Few Mexican coriander

* Handful of *Muktrubi* (Sichuan Pepper leaves)

*4-5 Pieces of *Ngari* (fermented fish paste)

*3-4 whole dried Red Chillies

*Turmeric powder 1 tsp.

*Garlic chives

*1 tsp of minced ginger

*1 tsp of coriander powder

*1 tsp of cumin seed

*2-3 bay leaves

* Salt to taste

Methods:

1. Put the snail, potato, ginger lily and chilli in a pressure cooker and cook till 2-3 whistle.

2. Take out the vegetables and snails from the pressure cooker and strain off the water.

3. Take out the red chillis in a separate bowl and mash them together with turmeric powder to paste.

4. Put all the potatoes and butterfly ginger lily and mash it along with the chilli paste.

5. Heat oil in a wok and add the bay leave then stir fry chive and ginger with the spices . Add washed *ngari* into this and cooked until the *ngari* become soft.

6. Now add the snails into the wok and stir fry with continuous stirring for around 2-3 min.

7. Now add Sichuan Pepper leaves, salt to taste, mash potato and butterfly ginger lily into the wok and stir fry for a minute

8. Add water in the wok until you get the desired consistency and bring it into boil for 10 min.

9. Garnish it with coriander and your *Lai Tharoi Thongba* (Manipuri River Snail Curry) is ready to serve.

